

Isolation, Characterization and Antibiotic Susceptibility of *Mycoplasma hominis* and *Ureaplasma urealyticum* from Infertile and Pregnant Women in Lagos, Nigeria

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between all authors. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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ABSTRACT

Background: *Mycoplasma hominis* and *Ureaplasma urealyticum* are potentially pathogenic agents, playing aetiological roles in both genital infections and infertility. In human in-vitro fertilization systems, the presence of *U. urealyticum* in either semen or female genital tract results in a decline of pregnancy rate per embryo transfer as well as neonatal infections. *M. hominis* has been associated with bacterial vaginosis, pelvic inflammatory disease, postabortal fever, and a number of gynecological infections.

Aim: The aim of this study is to isolate, characterize and determine the antibiotic susceptibility of *M. hominis* and *U. urealyticum* isolates from infertile and pregnant women in Lagos, Nigeria.

Materials and Methods: The samples were collected from Obstetrics and Gynaecology clinics of

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Lagos University Teaching Hospital and 68 Nigerian Army reference hospital Yaba. A total of 270 specimens of urine and HVS were collected from 135 women attending the clinics for routine consultations. One hundred and eighty HVS and urine specimens were from 90 married infertile women attending the clinics as part of a work-up for fertility investigations after failing to conceive for at least one year of unprotected sexual intercourse. Ninety HVS and urine specimens were from 45 pregnant women attending the clinics for routine antenatal care. None of the subjects expressed any symptom of genitourinary tract infections. All the specimens were inoculated into *Mycoplasma* broth and subsequently Blood Agar plates, incubated appropriately and identified. Antibiotic susceptibility tests were carried out on the 52 isolates. Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) was used to detect the organisms in all the collected specimens.

Results: Of the 90 HVS specimens collected from infertile women, 9 (10.0%) were positive for *M. hominis*, while 21 (23.3%) were positive for *U. urealyticum*. For the pregnant women using HVS specimens, 6 (13.3%) were positive for *M. hominis* while 5 (11.1%) were positive for *U. urealyticum*. The first void urine specimens gave lower values in both the infertile and pregnant women. Prevalence of *U. urealyticum* was higher in infertile women than in pregnant women ($p < 0.05$). The PCR technique gave higher values of 78.5% and 71.1% using HVS specimens for the infertile and pregnant women respectively for *Mycoplasma/Urealyticum* species. The antibiotic susceptibility test showed that all the isolates of *M. hominis* ($n=18$) were sensitive to Tetracycline (100%) and Ciprofloxacin (100%) while all the isolates of *U. urealyticum* ($n=34$) were sensitive to Tetracycline (100%) and Erythromycin (100%).

Conclusion: The significantly higher prevalence of *U. urealyticum* infection in infertile women (23.3%) compared to the lower prevalence in pregnant women (11.1%) may suggest that *U. urealyticum* can be incriminated in infertility. HVS specimen is preferred over urine specimens for the detection of *Mycoplasma* and *Ureaplasma*. Application of the PCR method, where affordable, is recommended for rapid and sensitive detection of *Mycoplasma* and *Ureaplasma* in HVS specimens. Tetracycline may be the antibiotic of choice, unless contraindicated, for the treatment of the infections, although the sample size was small.

Keywords: Prevalence; infertility; pregnancy; Nigeria; *Mycoplasma hominis*; *Ureaplasma urealyticum*.

1. INTRODUCTION

Infertility is considered when couples have been trying to achieve pregnancy with frequent sexual intercourse for at least a year without success [1]. Documented data revealed that approximately 72.4 million couples are infertile [1]. The causes of 25% of the cases of infertility are still unknown [2]. Majority of infertile females have inflammatory changes of the oviduct or the surrounding peritoneum and most of these alterations are caused by infections [3].

Generally, *Mycoplasma hominis* and *Ureaplasma urealyticum* have been isolated from genital mucosal surfaces, vagina and cervical parts of females [4,5,6]. *U. urealyticum* is a major cause of non-chlamydial and non-gonococcal urethritis, chorioamnionitis, acute prostatitis, vaginitis, cervicitis, preterm delivery and sepsis [6,7]. *M. hominis* is often associated with vaginitis, cervicitis, postpartum sepsis, pyelonephritis, preterm labour and premature birth [8,9]. Bacterial vaginosis is strongly implicated in female infertility and screening and treatment of

bacterial vaginosis during the course of infertility management increased the rate of pregnancy [10]. The genital *Mycoplasma* represent a complex and unique group of microorganisms that have been associated with a wide array of infectious diseases in adults and infants. These microorganisms particularly *U. urealyticum* are potentially pathogenic species playing etiologic roles in both genital infections and infertility. In human in vitro fertilization systems, it was reported that the presence of *U. urealyticum* in either semen or female genital tract resulted in a decline of pregnancy rates per embryo transfer [11], as well as neonatal infections [12]. Similarly, *M. hominis* has been associated with bacterial vaginosis, pelvic inflammatory disease and post abortal fever as well as a number of gynaecological infections [13]. The isolation of these organisms in the diagnostic laboratories is cumbersome and takes several days to achieve. The identification from clinical specimens using Nucleic Acid Amplification Test is very expensive for routine purposes. We therefore decided to determine the prevalence of *Mycoplasma* infections among infertile and pregnant women in Lagos Metropolis, Nigeria; and to determine the

susceptibility patterns of the isolates to some of the commonly prescribed antibiotics.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Ethical Issues

The study was approved by the Ethical Committees of Lagos University Teaching Hospital (LUTH) and the 68 Nigerian Army Reference Hospital, Yaba (68NARHY). All the participants signed informed consent form to participate in the study.

2.2 Inclusion Criteria

All the specimens (Urine and HVS) were from married infertile women attending the Gynecology Clinics as part of a work-up for fertility investigations after failing to conceive for at least one year of unprotected sexual intercourse. Also included in the study were expectant mothers who were normal antenatal clinic attendees for routine medical attention. Subjects with any clinical symptom of sexually transmitted disease were excluded from the study.

2.3 Sample Collection

From July 2012 to September 2012, a total of 270 HVS and urine specimens were collected from 135 women attending the clinics for routine consultations. One hundred and eighty of the specimens were from 90 married infertile women attending the clinics as part of a work-up for fertility investigations. Ninety specimens were from 45 pregnant women attending the clinics for routine antenatal care. The subjects were aged between 22-45 years. The HVS specimens were collected by clinicians using disposable speculum while the subjects were informed on how to collect the urine specimens devoid of contamination.

2.4 *Mycoplasma hominis* and *Ureaplasma urealyticum* Isolation and Identification

The specimens were inoculated into the *Mycoplasma* transport/growth medium without delay. Clearly labelled specimens were treated by inoculating 0.1 ml into 5 ml of prepared *Mycoplasma* broth at the site of specimen collection and transported to the laboratory. The remaining urine specimens (about 10 ml each) were stored at -70°C. Both the urine and HVS

specimens were incubated for up to 48 h at 37°C in 5% CO₂ for *Ureaplasma urealyticum* and up to 5 days for *Mycoplasma hominis*. These were examined daily for turbidity as evidence of growth. Subsequently, the broth cultures were subcultured onto solid blood agar media and incubated at 37°C in 5% CO₂ for 24 to 48 hours for *Ureaplasma urealyticum* and up to 5 days for *Mycoplasma hominis*. Urea for urease activities and L-arginine for arginine utilization were used for biochemical tests. Strains of *M. hominis* ATCC 23114 and *U. urealyticum* ATCC 33175 were used as positive controls. Colonies presenting a fried egg appearance suggested the presence of *M. hominis*, while colonies that were brown and tiny indicated the presence of *U. urealyticum*. *U. urealyticum* also hydrolyzed urea while *M. hominis* metabolized the L. arginine [14].

2.5 Polymerase Chain Reaction Confirmation of *U. urealyticum* and *M. hominis*

A PCR technique was used to detect *U. urealyticum* and *M. hominis*. Two millilitres of urine and HVS broth specimens was used Ref: standard strains of *U. urealyticum* (ATCC 33175); *M. hominis* (ATCC 23114) and *Clostridium difficile* (ATCC BA-2155) were used. The PCR was carried out in an Eppendorf Nexus thermal cycler (E6331000025) with the following cycling parameters; an initial denaturation set up at 95°C for 10 minutes, followed by 30 consecutive cycles of denaturation at 95°C for 30 seconds, annealing at 56°C for 30 consecutive cycles. After this, a final extension at 72°C for 5 minutes was carried out.

High vaginal swab (HVS) specimens and 2 ml of first void urine from each subject were directly inoculated into 5 ml of *Mycoplasma* broth, mixed and transported to the laboratory at the Nigerian Institute of Medical Research, (NIMR), Yaba, Lagos.

2.6 Sample Preparation [15]

Two milliliters of first void urine sample and HVS suspension from each of the subjects were put into a sterile 5ml tube and centrifuged at 13,000 rpm for 5 minutes. The supernatant is discarded and the cell pellets were resuspended in 50 microlitre of lysis buffer. After the homogenization, the cell pellets were incubated at 37°C for 15 minutes so as to lyse the cells and

degrade the proteins. The samples were heated at 95°C for 10 minutes to inactivate the protease and then centrifuged at 13,000 rpm for 5 minutes to sediment the cell debris [15]. The supernatants were transferred into new microcentrifuge tubes. Positive and negative controls were set up along side the kit controls.

The standard strains of control organisms are; *Ureaplasma urealyticum* – ATCC 33175, *Mycoplasma hominis* – ATCC 23114, strain PG 21, and *Clostridium difficile* – ATCC BA – 2155, Strain LBM 0801058. The primers My UU-Forward 5¹– TGG AGT TAA GTC GTA ACA AG-3 and My UU reverse r 5¹– CTA AGA TGT TTC ACT TCA CC-3, were obtained from NIMR, Yaba, Lagos.

2.7 PCR Reaction Setup

Twenty microliters of each of the universal PCR mix was transferred into a tube, 2.5 microliters of the universal primers and 2.5 microliters of the test samples were added and mixed gently using a voltex mixer. Positive and negative samples were set up alongside the controls. The tools were placed in a thermal cycler and were taken through the three steps of amplification procedure.

2.8 Gel Electrophoresis Protocol

Five microliters of the PCR product is added to 1.5 microliter of loading buffer, and mixed thoroughly. The samples and a DNA marker (1000 bp ladder) were loaded on the 3% agarose gel. Positive and negative controls were set up alongside the kit controls. Electrophoresis was allowed to run until the tracking dye has migrated 60-70% of the gel length. The gel was then stained with ethidium bromide and viewed with ultraviolet illumination.

The kit detects 10⁻⁹ microgram quantities of target DNA. Samples that were positive for the presence of *Mycoplasmas* showed a distinct band at 434-468 bp. The positive control exhibited a 464 bp band while no visible band was noticed in the negative control lane.

2.9 Antimicrobial Susceptibility Test on the Isolates

Antimicrobial susceptibility test was carried out on the isolates using the modified Kirby-Bauer method [16] with Tetracycline (30 µg), Gentamycin (10 µg), Erythromycin (15 µg),

Streptomycin (30 µg) and Ciprofloxacin (5 µg). Statistical analysis was done using SPSS version 10 (computer software).

3. RESULTS

A total of 90 High Vaginal Swabs from infertile women and 45 HVS specimens from pregnant women were analysed using culture methods and PCR for *M. hominis* and *U. urealyticum*. Out of the 90 HVS specimens from the infertile women, 9 (10.0%) were positive for *M. hominis* while 21 (23.3%) were positive for *U. urealyticum*. The urine specimens from both the infertile and pregnant women gave lower prevalences of 3.3% for *M. hominis*, 6.7% for *U. urealyticum* and 0.0% for *M. hominis*, 4.4% for *U. urealyticum* respectively (Table 1). HVS specimens yielded more isolates than the urine specimens ($\chi^2=72.174$; $P<0.05$).

Table 2 shows the distribution of *Mycoplasma/Ureaplasma* organisms in infertile and pregnant women in the study area. Out of the 45 HVS specimens from the pregnant women, 32 (71.1%) were *Mycoplasma/Ureaplasma*. The 78 analysed urine specimens from the infertile women gave a prevalence of 58.9% of *Mycoplasma/Ureaplasma* infections. For the pregnant women, out of the screened 45 urine specimens 12 (26.6%) were positive for *Mycoplasma/Ureaplasma*.

The antibiotic susceptibility patterns of the *M. hominis* and *U. urealyticum* is shown in Table 3. *M. hominis* showed 100% sensitivity to Tetracycline and Ciprofloxacin while *U. urealyticum* showed 100% sensitivity to Tetracycline and Erythromycin.

4. DISCUSSION

The results of our study showed that *M. hominis* and *U. urealyticum* infections are prevalent among the infertile and pregnant women in Lagos Metropolis, Nigeria. In this study both the HVS and Urine specimens were examined using culture and PCR techniques. The culture technique gave a prevalence, using the HVS specimens, of *M. hominis* (10.0%) and 13.3% for infertile and pregnant women respectively. The urine specimens yielded lower values for *M. hominis* with a prevalence of 3.3% and 0.0% for infertile and pregnant women respectively. A prevalence of 6.7% for infertile women and 4.4% for pregnant women were recorded for *U. urealyticum* infection. The PCR technique

expectedly gave higher prevalence of 78.5% and 71.1% using HVS specimens for *Mycoplasma/Ureaplasma* in infertile and pregnant women respectively. The urine specimens gave lower values of 58.9% and 26.6% for *Mycoplasma/Ureaplasma* infection in infertile and pregnant women respectively. The urine specimens gave lower values of 58.9% and 26.6% for *Mycoplasma/Ureaplasma* infection in infertile and pregnant women respectively. One possible explanation for the higher prevalences of these infections in infertile women is hormonal disorders which can lead to reduced levels of immunity and increased bacterial colonization and survival in the vaginal epithelium [17].

In addition to the considerably high prevalence of *M. hominis* and *U. urealyticum* infections in our

study, several published report revealed various prevalence rates. Agbakoba et al. [17] reported a prevalence of 35.7% in women of reproductive age in Ibadan. The prevalence rate of *M. hominis* and *U. urealyticum* in HVS specimens ranged from 0 to 3.8% [18,19]. The prevalence of *U. urealyticum* infection was 20%, 41.9% and 51.5% in South Africa, Italy and Africa respectively [18].

In a survey of 1000 female students at University of Calabar, Lennox et al. [20] showed that 70% were infected with vaginosis and vaginitis out of which 51% had single infection while 19% had mixed infections. The varied prevalence rates all over the world may be due to the use of only culture methods or PCR. In addition there are many factors that will affect the culture results

Table 1. Distribution of *M. hominis* and *U. urealyticum* in infertile (n=90) and pregnant (n=45) women in Lagos, Nigeria

Source	Organism	No. of isolates	Percentage
Infertile women			
HVS	<i>M. hominis</i>	9	10.0
	<i>U. urealyticum</i>	21	23.3
Urine	<i>M. hominis</i>	3	3.30
	<i>U. urealyticum</i>	6	6.70
Pregnant women			
HVS	<i>M. hominis</i>	6	13.30
	<i>U. urealyticum</i>	5	11.10
Urine	<i>M. hominis</i>	0	0.00
	<i>U. urealyticum</i>	2	4.40

Table 2. Distribution of *Mycoplasma/Ureaplasma* species in infertile and pregnant women in Lagos, Nigeria using PCR

Source	Organism	No. of isolates	Percentage
Infertile women			
HVS (n=65)	<i>Mycoplasma/Ureaplasma</i>	51	78.5
Urine (n=78)	<i>Mycoplasma/Ureaplasma</i>	46	58.9
Pregnant women			
HVS (n=45)	<i>Mycoplasma/Ureaplasma</i>	32	71.1
Urine (n=45)	<i>Mycoplasma/Ureaplasma</i>	12	26.6

Table 3. Antimicrobial susceptibility patterns of *M. hominis* and *U. urealyticum* isolated from infertile and pregnant women in Lagos, Nigeria

Source	Organism	No. of isolates	Antimicrobial agent activities % sensitive				
			Te	CN	E	CPX	S
HVS	<i>M. hominis</i>	15	15(100)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	15(100)	0(0.0)
	<i>U. urealyticum</i>	26	26(100)	0(0.0)	26(100)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)
Urine	<i>M. hominis</i>	3	3(100)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3(100)	0(0.0)
	<i>U. urealyticum</i>	8	8(100)	0(0.0)	8(100)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)
Total		52	52(100)	0(0.0)	34(65.4)	18(34.6)	0(0.0)

Key: Te = Tetracycline (30 µg); CN=Gentamycin (10 µg); E=Erythromycin (15 µg); CPX=Ciprofloxacin (5 µg); S=Streptomycin (30 µg)

such as the use of transport medium, the duration between the collection of the sample and the inoculation and the duration of incubation. The Nucleic Acid Amplification tests gave higher results due to its sensitivity and it is also a rapid test, although it is more expensive.

In our study, it was observed that *M. hominis* and *U. urealyticum* were detected more from HVS than urine specimens. This is in agreement with Taylor-Robinson [21] who reported that the numbers of isolates from urine specimens were usually 10 fold less than in swabs.

In vitro antibiotic susceptibility test showed that all the isolates of *M. hominis* and *U. urealyticum* were sensitive to Tetracycline (100%). *U. urealyticum* isolates in addition to Tetracycline were all sensitive to Erythromycin, while all *M. hominis* isolates were also sensitive to Ciprofloxacin.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, our research showed that *M. hominis* and *U. urealyticum* infections are prevalent in both the infertile and pregnant women in Lagos metropolis. Efforts, where feasible, should be made to detect the presence of these organisms during the work-up of cases of infertility and in pregnancy to prevent the adverse outcomes. We therefore recommend the precise monitoring of fertile and infertile females for the presence of *M. hominis* and *U. urealyticum* and treatment of positive cases to prevent diseases and possibly infertility.

The small sample size, and the lower number of recruited pregnant women compared with the infertile women are limiting factors in the present study. It is hoped that in future, a larger sample size will allow us to make definite conclusions.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

REFERENCES

1. Boivin J, Bunting L, Collins JA. International estimates of infertility prevalence and treatment-seeking: Potential need and demand for infertility medical care. Hum Reprod. 2007;22(16):1506-1512.
2. Daar AS, Merali Z. Infertility and social suffering: The case of ART in developing countries. In: Vayena E, Rowe P, Griffin D, editors. Report of a meeting on Medical, ethical and social aspects of assisted reproduction. Geneva: WHO. 2001;16-21.
3. Wiesenfeld HC, Hillier SL, Meyn LA. Subclinical pelvic inflammatory disease and infertility. Obstet Gynecol. 2012; 120(1):37-43. DOI: 10.1097/AOG.Ob 013e31825a6bc9 [PubMed][Cross Ref]
4. Capoccia R, Greub G, Baud D. *Ureaplasma urealyticum*, *Mycoplasma hominis* and adverse pregnancy outcomes. Curr Opin Infect Dis. 2013;26(3):231-240. DOI: 10.1097/QCO.Ob013e328360db58. [PubMed][Cross Ref]
5. Wang QY, Li RH, Zheng LQ. Prevalence and antimicrobial susceptibility of *Ureaplasma urealyticum* and *Mycoplasma hominis* in female outpatients, 2009-2013. J Microbiol, Immunol Infection; 2009-2013. [PubMed].
6. Al-Sweih NA, Al-Fadli AH, Omu AE. Prevalence of *Chlamydia trachomatis*, *Mycoplasma hominis*, *Mycoplasma genitalium* and *Ureaplasma urealyticum* infections and seminal quality in infertile and fertile men in Kuwait. J Androl. 2012; 33(6):1323-1329. DOI: 10.2164/jandrol.111.013821. [PubMed] [Cross Ref].
7. Zhu C, Liu J, Ling Y. Prevalence and antimicrobial susceptibility of *Ureaplasma urealyticum* and *Mycoplasma hominis* in Chinese women with genital infectious diseases. Indian J Dermatol, Venereology, Leprology. 2012;78(3):406-407. [PubMed].
8. Aydin Y, Atis A, Ocer F. Association of cervical infection of *Chlamydia trachomatis*, *Ureaplasma urealyticum* and *Mycoplasma hominis* with peritoneum colonization in pregnancy. J Obstet Gynecol. 2010;30(8):809-812. DOI: 10.3109/01443615.2010.519063 [PubMed][Cross Ref]
9. Campos GB, Lobao TN, Selis NN. Prevalence of *Mycoplasma genitalium* and *Mycoplasma hominis* in urogenital tract of Brazilian Women. BMC Infect Dis. 2015;15(1):60. [PMC free article][PubMed]

10. Salah RM, Allam AM, Magdy AM. Bacterial vaginosis and infertility: Cause or association? Eur J. Obstet Gynecol Reprod Biol. 2013;167(1):59-63. DOI: 10.1016/j. ejogrb. 2012.10.031 [Pub Med] [Cross Ref]
11. Reichart M, Kalane I, Bartoov B. *In vivo* and *in vitro* impairment of human and ram sperm nuclear chromatin integrity by sexually transmitted *Ureaplasma Urealyticum*. Infectious Biological Reproduction. 2000;(63):1041-1048.
12. Hentshel J, Abele-Horn M, Peters J. *Ureaplasma Urealyticum* in the cerebrospinal fluid of premature infants. Acta Paediatrica. 1993;82:690-693.
13. Yoshida T, Maeda S, Deguchi T, Ishiko H. Phylogeny- based rapid identification of *Mycoplasma* and *Ureaplasma* from urethritis patients. Journal of Clinical Microbiology. 2002;40:105-110.
14. Donald C, Lehman Connie R, Mahon. *Mycoplasma* and *ureaplasma*. In: Textbook of Diagnostic Microbiology, 4th ed. 564-574. W.B. Saunders Company; 2011.
15. Kwok S. Procedures to minimize PCR product carry-over. In: PCR protocols: A guide to methods and applications (Innis MA, Gelfand DH, Sininsky JJ, White TJ, eds.) Academic Press, San Diego. 1990; 142-146.
16. Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute: Methods for antimicrobial dilution and disk susceptibility testing of infrequently isolated or fastidious bacteria, approved guideline M45-A Wayne, Pa, CLSI; 2005.
17. Kornats'ka AH. Local humoral immunity in women with combined forms of infertility. Liksprava. 1998;4:82-84. [PubMed].
18. Agbakoba NR, Adetosoye AI, Adewole IF. Presence of *mycoplasma* and *ureaplasma* species in the vagina of women of reproductive age. West Afr J Med. 2007;26(1).
19. Leli C, Mencacci A, Bombaci JC. Prevalence and antimicrobial susceptibility of *Ureaplasma urealyticum* and *Mycoplasma hominis* population of Italian and immigrant outpatients. Infez Med. [PubMed]. 2012;20(2):82-87.
20. Lennox JA, Abbey SD, Udiba D, Mbotto CI, Ikpoh IS, Akubueyi FC. Prevalence of vaginitis and vaginosis among University of Calabar female students. Journal of Public Health and Epidemiology. 2013;5(4): 167-172.
21. Taylor-Robinson D. Genital *mycoplasma* infection. Clin. Lab. Med. 1989;9:501-523.

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